

The Study of Phospholipids in the Oil of the Husk of *Oriza sativa*

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In the present work the phospholipids have been extracted from rice and wheat husk oils. A detailed study of phospholipids from the "Rice-husk oil" has been described.

Many phospholipids have been isolated from plants; cephalins, lecithins are reported to be present in 12 species of Leguminous seeds¹. The Lipids are also extracted from leaves with hot isopropyl alcohol².

Helianthus annuus and starch-containing *Phaseolus vulgaris* seeds show the synthesis of lecithin during ripening. Some synthesis of lecithin is detected in air-dry seeds³. Pure lecithin is obtained from soybean by extracting with hexane⁴. The amount of phospholipids increases in the germination of soybean. Phosphorus was maximum at 2nd day and minimum on the 5th day⁵. The increase in phosphatide is due to augmentation of lecithin and phospho-inositol and this has been studied by Levene and Rolf⁶. Roth and Schuster⁷ state that most seed phosphatides contain 70 to 80% of lecithin with 20 to 30% cephalin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Separation of Phospholipids: The lecithin and cephalin are separated from other lipids by adding acetone in which they are insoluble while other lipids are soluble. Cephalin is separated from the lecithin by adding absolute alcohol in which it is not soluble while lecithin is soluble. They are separated from other water soluble impurities by adding acetone in water suspension and rejecting the filtrate. The residue is dissolved in benzene solution and cadmium chloride solution is added to make cephalin free from other organic impurities. The solution is filtered and residue rejected. Acetone or absolute alcohol is added to filtrate to reprecipitate cephalin.

Separation of Cephalin: The rice husk oil was dissolved in acetone. Some portion of the oil did not dissolve in acetone indicating the presence of phospholipids. The substance was found to be insoluble in alcohol showing the presence of cephalin. The percentage of phospholipids was calculated and it was found that 19.1% phospholipid was present in rice husk oil.

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Purification : The substance was purified from water soluble impurities by dissolving the residue in water and reprecipitating by adding acetone in the water suspension. The phospholipid was further purified from organic impurities by cadmium chloride solution and again reprecipitated by acetone. It was further extracted with ether and finally by warm absolute ethanol. The substance was dried and weighed and was found to be 15%.

The substance was further purified by extracting the lipid in ether and was allowed to stand in cold. The precipitate was dispersed in water and was treated with normal hydrochloric acid and a cheese-like precipitate was obtained which was separated by centrifugation, washed with acetone and dried in vacuum.

RESULTS

The waxy substance was soluble in benzene, chloroform and ether. When freshly obtained it was white in colour but on exposure to atmosphere it turned yellowish and finally brown. The compound was titrated with *N*/50 potassium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The substance reacted in equivalent amount with potassium hydroxide indicating that the substance is monobasic acid, having one free hydrogen of phosphoric acid molecule, present in the compound. It gave the test of unsaturation by potassium permanganate and bromine solution.

Since the substance on combustion did not produce a sooty flame and since there was no reduction of Fehling's solution nor any effervescence with sodium carbonate, aldehydic and carboxylic groups were absent. The substance was dissolved in ether and boiled with conc. HNO_3 , which was further boiled after adding ammonium molybdate solution and a canary yellow precipitate was obtained showing the presence of phosphate radical. The substance gave the test for nitrogen present in the molecule. The substance on saponification gave a mixture of sodium salts of fatty acids which were identified as stearic and oleic acids.

The infra-red spectra of the substance was taken in chloroform medium and gave the following characteristic peaks in the region of wave lengths which corresponded to characteristic groups :

Region of wave length in cm^{-1}	Characteristic groups
3400	$-\text{NH}_2$
1030	P-O-C (alkyl) (1000-1050)
1230	P = O
1630	$-\text{C}-\text{C}$ (aliphatic)
1735	$-\text{C} = \text{O}$ (ester)
720	$-(\text{CH}_2)_n$ ($n > 4$)
2860	$-\text{CH} = \text{CH}-$
2920	$-\text{CH}_3$
1455	$-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ (Asymmetrical)
860	$-\text{C}-\text{C}$ -(Skeletal)

The general absorption pattern comprising a strong band at 5.73μ , a strong band at 8.5μ flanked by bands near 8 and 9μ and a band near 13.9μ , resembles those for long chain glycerides. The characteristic shift of strong absorption band at 5.85μ of the long chain fatty acid spectra from 5.73μ in the ester spectra was also found in the cephalin spectra.

On ultimate analysis by combustion the following results were obtained :

Elements	Observed values	Calculated values
Carbon	68.14%	67.49%
Hydrogen	12.01%	10.97%
Nitrogen	2.02%	1.91%
Phosphorus	4.30%	4.25%
Molecular weight	730.24	729.00

On the basis of the above results it may be concluded that the compound contains stearic and oleic acids which may be present as esters, because they were obtained after saponification and acidification. The compound may contain free NH_2 and P-O or P=O linkages.

Thus the aliphatic compound having unsaturation, which may be present in the acid molecule, may have the following structure :

Cephalin.

DISCUSSION

The percentage of cephalin present in the rice husk oil is quite high as compared to that in other oils. The cephalin helps in the development of brain cells. It also helps in blood clotting in which phosphatidyl ethanol amine are most active⁸. The cephalin fraction of the phosphatides naturally occurring in linseed oil strongly inhibits the glycerolysis of triglycerides by inactivation of the catalyst, sodium hydroxide⁹. Cephalin helps and increases the affinity of antimalarial drugs for erythrocytes¹⁰. Conversion of cephalin to lecithin has been reviewed by Hildegard Debuck¹¹. Therapeutic action of cephalin extracted from ox brain has been found in psychoneurotic and neurodystonic states¹².

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